

ISic3641

I.Sicily inscription 3641

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building (?)

Material

sandstone (?)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Contrada Canalicchio, proprieta Signorina Ch. Reimann, Feb. 1962

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro

Greco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645707

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 191-192 tav.69.1

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3641. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388884>